

REQUIREMENTS FOR DRIVERS OF MOTOR VEHICLES

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Abstract: The article discusses the legal norms and documents of the Republic of Uzbekistan regarding vehicles. The legislative norms on what documents each driver of a car must keep with him, in what cases and from whom they can be requested, as well as special driver's licenses established for each type of vehicle and mechanisms for their verification are indicated. In particular, the documents established by state bodies (IXX and consular institutions), special requirements for driving international motor vehicles, and methods for verifying personal information are discussed.

Keywords: vehicles, driver's license, legislation, traffic rules.

Introduction A driver of a mechanical vehicle must carry the following documents with them and present them to traffic police officers upon request a driving license authorizing them to operate the appropriate category of vehicle the stub of the license if it is an old type driving license a temporary permit if the license has been temporarily confiscated and an identity document when operating the vehicle with a temporary permit a registration certificate for the vehicle excluding mopeds and if the driver is not the owner of the vehicle a document confirming ownership or the right to use and dispose of the vehicle close relatives of the vehicle owner such as parents spouses children siblings are exempt from this requirement the driver must also have the compulsory civil liability insurance policy of the vehicle owner available in paper or electronic form

When a vehicle marked for a person with a disability is driven by a person with a first or second group disability a document confirming the disability must be presented if required by law licenses certificates authorizing the operation of a vehicle issued by a legal entity or documents for the transported cargo must be available drivers of vehicles owned by legal entities must also have a certificate confirming completion of professional training including passenger or cargo transport activities

Main Section Drivers of foreign vehicles additionally must have a "Vehicle Re-export Commitment" and a receipt confirming payment of the mandatory fee for passenger cars with tinted windows Traffic police officers check the following documents via tablet a notarized power of attorney or certificate granting the right to use and operate the vehicle a permit to tint vehicle windows and information confirming that the vehicle has passed technical inspection

If the driver carries a passport or ID card issued by the internal affairs bodies or consular offices of the Republic of Uzbekistan documents confirming the right to operate the vehicle registration certificates ownership or usage rights of the vehicle documents issued by a legal entity authorizing use of the vehicle or cargo documents are not required

The driver must hold a driving license for the appropriate vehicle category A for mopeds motorcycles and similar vehicles B for vehicles with a maximum authorized weight not exceeding 3500 kilograms or with no more than eight passenger seats in addition to the driver's

seat including trailers up to 750 kilograms C for vehicles over 3500 kilograms and trailers up to 750 kilograms D for passenger vehicles with more than eight passenger seats and trailers up to 750 kilograms BE for B category vehicles with trailers over 750 kilograms CE for C category vehicles with trailers over 750 kilograms DE for D category vehicles with trailers over 750 kilograms only tram drivers may operate trams and trolleybus drivers may operate trolleybuses

A person may operate a vehicle that does not belong to them only if the owner is present or if they have a notarized power of attorney or a certificate authorizing use and management and if the compulsory civil liability insurance policy of the vehicle owner allows the designated person to operate it independent of the owner's presence close relatives of the vehicle owner listed in the insurance policy may use the vehicle independently

Drivers and front-seat passengers of vehicles equipped with safety belts must fasten their seat belts before starting the vehicle

Conclusion This article highlights the legal framework for vehicles in Uzbekistan and the importance of documents granting the right to operate them it explains which documents drivers must carry how they can be checked and the procedures for compliance it also covers the specific driving license categories required for different vehicles and the inspection procedures necessary to ensure safety and legal order

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